

Snapshots of Cygnus A reconstruction at 4811 MHz, 8427 MHz, and 13360 MHz

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In the paper “**fast-resolve**: Fast Bayesian Radio Interferometric Imaging”, snapshots of the reconstruction of the VLA Cygnus A S-band data are discussed to analyze the convergence speed of **resolve** and **fast-resolve**. The same comparison but for the C-band data is displayed in Fig. 1. The grid size we used for the C-band sky map is a factor of two larger along both spatial axes. Thus, in total, we have four times as many pixels, increasing the computational cost of the algorithm. On the A100 GPU, the **fast-resolve** reconstruction was finished after 56 min, while on the RTX 3090 GPU, the reconstruction took 165 min. We believe that the larger difference between the two GPUs for the C-band data compared to the S-band data might be because, for the smaller grid size of the S-band reconstruction, the A100 GPUs were not fully utilized. As for the S-band data **fast-resolve** was run for 20 major cycles. For completeness, we also display snapshots of the X- and Ku-band reconstructions in Fig. 2. These reconstructions were only carried out on the A100 GPU. After 132 min both reconstructions were finished. Again 20 major cycles were executed.

Figure 1: Snapshots of *fast-resolve* reconstructions of the 4811 MHz Cygnus A data. On an NVIDIA A100 GPU *fast-resolve* is 2 – 3 times faster than on an NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU. The same number of major and minor iterations are performed on both GPUs. Since the reconstruction on the A100 GPU is finished after 56 min, the bottom left panel is identical to the row above.

Figure 2: Snapshots of the **fast-resolve** Cygnus A reconstruction of the 8427 MHz and 13360 MHz data on a NVIDIA A100 GPU. The wall time after which the snapshot was taken is indicated in the bottom left of each panel.